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A STUDY ON BRAND PREFERENCE OF TWO-WHEELERS IN PALAYAMKOTTAI

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Abstract

India is the second largest two-wheeler market in the world. Two wheelers play a vital role in the individual's life. This study focuses how consumers are preferred two wheelers for their convenient lifestyle. In the fast-moving world consumers brand preference and two wheelers are interrelated. Brand preference, purchasing power and utilization are discussed in their study.

Keywords: Two-wheeler, Brand preference

Introduction:

The two-wheeler industry in our country is constantly growing. It is really amazing how two-wheeler markets have developed on in the last two decades, the Indian two-wheeler industry has finally transformed to this level of achievement. As an insight of the fact that consumer brand preference towards two-wheeler turn modernity. The result of liberalisation and globalisation surfaced way people in rural areas did not want to wait or the bus, automatically their preference turn towards two-wheeler. Today effectual consumer brand preferences of two-wheeler are individual into mass, segment demand, reliability, Modern styling, economy and purchasing power.

Objectives of the study:

- To study about the demographic factors of the respondents.
- To know about the brand preferences of two wheelers of sample respondents.
- To find the purpose of usage brand preferences and mode of purchase of two-wheelers of sample respondents.
- To know about the satisfaction level of influencing factors of two-wheeler purchase.

Hypotheses of the Study:

In order to achieve the above-mentioned objectives following null hypotheses have been formulated and suitable statistical tools have been applied.

H₀₁: There is no association between income and mode of purchase of the motorcycle.

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Data used:

Primary as well as secondary data have been used. The secondary data have been collected through books, Journals, Magazines, News Papers, Websites and other already published data. The primary data have been collected through a well-constructed Questionnaire having thirty-eight questions. Data have been collected from 50 respondents at Palayamkottai during the month of Jan 2019.

Tools for analysis:

Simple percentage method, Garrett Ranking Technique, Chi- square test is applied.

Limitation of the study:

- The study area is limited to Palayamkottai.
- Time and resources were major constraint to complete the entire work because of it.
- Only 50 respondents are taken for the study.

Table 1: Demographic Profile of the respondents

Variables	Particulars	Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	30	60
	Female	20	40
Age	Up to 20	10	20
	21-30	20	40
	31-40	11	22
	Above 40	9	18
Educational Status	Up to school level	5	10
	Degree/Diploma	25	50
	Professional	15	30
	Other	5	10
Income	Up to 10,000	11	22
	10,000-20,000	20	40
	20,000-30,000	14	28
	Above 30,000	5	10

Source: Primary Data

From the above table it is revealed that

- 60 percent respondents are male, and 40 percent are female.
- 20 numbers of respondents are in the age group of 21-30 years.
- 50 percent respondents are completed their UG Degree.
- 40 percent of the respondents have the monthly income of ₹ 10,000 to ₹ 20,000.

Table 2: Brand Preference

Sl. No.	Models	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	Hero	10	20
2	Honda	20	40
3	TVS	5	10
4	Bajaj	5	10
5	Yamaha	10	20
	Total	50	100

Source: Primary Data

The above table shows that out of 50 respondents, 20 percent of the respondents are using Hero motor cycle, 40 percent of the respondent's

brand of two-wheeler is Honda motor cycle, 10 percent of the respondents are using TVS motor cycle, 10 percent of the respondents travelling by Bajaj motor cycle, and 20 percent of the respondents using Yamaha motor cycle. Majority of the respondent's brand of two-wheeler is Honda.

Table 3: Mode of Purchase

Sl. No.	Mode	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	Cash	33	66
2	Loan	17	34
	Total	50	100

Source: Primary Data

The above table shows that out of 50 respondents, 66 percent respondents are bought through cash, and 34 percent of the respondents are bought through loan, therefore 66 percent of the respondents are bought through cash.

Table 4: Priority of usage

Sl. No.	Purpose of use	Mean score	Rank
1	For Studies	7.05	I
2	For Office	6.08	II
3	For Business	5.02	III
4	For Shopping	3.64	IV
5	For Others	2.24	V

Source: Primary Data

The above table shows that priority of usage of bike that for studies was first ranged with mean score of 7.05, for office was second ranged with mean score of 6.08, for business was third ranged with mean score of 5.02, fourth and fifth ranged mean score of 3.64 and 2.24 respectively.

Table 5: Satisfaction level on influencing factors

Sl. No.	Particulars	HS	S	M	DS	HDS	TOTAL
1	Brand image	18 (36)	7 (14)	9 (18)	11 (22)	5 (10)	50 (100)
2	Fuel economy	15 (30)	5 (10)	8 (16)	12 (24)	10 (20)	50 (100)
3	Maintenance cost	13 (26)	7 (14)	13 (26)	15 (30)	2 (4)	50 (100)
4	Pick-up	12 (24)	18 (36)	13 (26)	1 (2)	6 (12)	50 (100)
5	Elegant appeal	10 (20)	11 (22)	9 (18)	13 (26)	7 (14)	50 (100)
6	Availability of vehicle	13 (26)	9 (18)	6 (12)	8 (16)	14 (28)	50 (100)
7	Resale value	8 (16)	18 (36)	7 (14)	3 (6)	14 (28)	50 (100)
8	Finance facility	5 (10)	20 (40)	12 (24)	8 (16)	7 (14)	50 (100)
9	After sale service	9 (18)	17 (34)	11 (22)	5 (10)	8 (16)	50 (100)

Source: Primary data

The above table shows that 36 percent of the respondents highly satisfied with brand image and 10 percent of the respondents highly dissatisfaction with brand image. 30 percent of the respondents highly satisfied with fuel economy and 20 percent of the respondents highly dissatisfaction with fuel economy. 26percent of the respondents highly satisfied with maintenance cost and 4 percent of the respondents highly dissatisfaction with maintenance cost.

24 percent of the respondents highly satisfied with pick up and 12 percent of the respondents highly dissatisfaction with pick up. 20 percent of the respondents highly satisfied with elegant a peal and 14 percent of the respondents highly dissatisfaction with elegant appeal. 26percent of the respondents highly satisfied with availability of vehicle and 28 percent of the respondents highly dissatisfaction with availability of vehicle.

H₀₁: There is no association between income and mode of purchase of the motorcycle.

Table 6.1: Observed frequency

Sl. No.	Income	Mode of purchase		Total
		Cash	Loan	
1	Up to ₹ 10,000	5	6	11
2	₹ 10,000 - 20,000	6	8	14
3	₹ 20,000 - 30,000	18	02	20
4	₹ Above 30,000	4	1	5
	Total	33	17	50

Source: Primary data

Table 6.2: Expected frequency

Sl. No.	Income	Mode of purchase		Total
		Cash	Loan	
1	Up to ₹ 10,000	7.26	3.74	11
2	₹ 10,000 - 20,000	9.24	4.76	14
3	₹ 20,000 - 30,000	13.02	6.08	20
4	₹ Above 30,000	3.03	1.07	5
	Total	33	17	50

Source: Computed Primary data

Table 6.3: Association between income and mode of purchase of motorcycle

O	E	O-E	(O-E) ²	$\frac{(O-E)^2}{E}$
5	7.26	-2.26	5.11	0.70
6	9.24	-3.24	10.05	1.13
18	13.02	4.08	23.04	1.74
4	3.03	0.07	0.05	0.15
6	3.74	2.26	5.11	1.36
8	4.76	3.24	10.05	2.20
2	6.08	-4.08	23.04	3.38
1	1.07	-0.07	0.05	0.29
				10.95

Calculated value is 10.95 Table value is 7.815 (3 @5%)

The calculated value is more than table value, the hypothesis is rejected. Hence there is an association between income and brand preference of the motorcycle.

Finding:

- Nearly three fourth of the respondents are male and male respondents are covered more in number.
- Youngster is covered for the study more in number.
- Majority of the respondents fall under the income group of between 10,000-20,000.
- Honda motorcycles are the highly preferred brand in Palayamkottai.
- Majority of the respondents are purchase motorcycle through cash.

Conclusion:

Every year new difference of two wheelers is introduced into the market. In today competitive environment many national and multinational two-wheeler industries have gained remarkably by taking notice of consumer preference innovative marketing strategies and sale promotion. The study of the consumer can help the individuals to understand more about the psychological, sociological, and economic factors that influence human behaviours. From the study, it is evident that many individuals brand preference of two-wheeler is Honda. Therefore, to complete with Honda all worldwide competitors and home country manufacture of two-wheeler have concentrate more on their brands to acquire more customers in India.

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